

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-3-260-IA-2% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230308
Vial:	10	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 3 260
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	18.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/8/2023 11:57:25 AM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 2:43:17 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.182	251250	43.77	16596
2	8.835	251740	43.85	17135
3	11.389	34472	6.01	2054
4	14.214	36577	6.37	1781

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-3-254-IA-2% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230308
Vial:	11	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 3 254
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	18.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/8/2023 12:16:06 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 2:45:33 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.176	2355733	99.17	163452
2	8.865	8163	0.34	780
3	11.457	5727	0.24	482
4	14.440	5775	0.24	506